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INTERACTION DESIGN OF E-BOOKS FOR MOBILE VALUE-ADDED SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on examining the impact that mobile value-added services may have on the process of digital learning. We explore many types of e-book readers that have been developed for the iPad, and summarize the application of gestures to communicate with a touch screen. The study analyzes popular user interfaces designs based on the characteristics of good interaction design proposed by Saffer in 2006, to assess the user interface of interactive e-books. It discusses the interface of e-books that users read and places emphasis on key points for operation gestures, content plans and interaction design. User testing was adopted to study the interaction design in reading e-books based on mobile devices. The study concludes that the participants' opinions of e-books were fairly neutral in user testing, discusses value-added services of e-books and provides a case study for the creative cooperation model. The paper offers the features of value-added services for the development and improvement of interactive e-books in the future.

Keywords: Interaction design, Value-added services, E-books.

INTRODUCTION

Publishing and book markets are undergoing a transformation due to the Internet and the emerging e-book technology. In April 2010, Apple released its iPad tablet computer, which targets several media markets including e-books (Jiang & Katsamakos, 2010). Publishers around the world are striving to embrace the digital age – to build distinctive brands, develop sustainable business strategies, achieve greater profitability, and deliver optimized content to

fragmented audiences on an expanding array of smartphones, tablets, e-readers, and other devices. Audiences seek compelling, media-rich experiences wherever they go, using their preferred devices. This paper focuses on examining the impact that mobile value-added services may have on the process of digital learning. The value characteristics of this research are as follows:

- This study integrates user requirements into e-book interaction design. It discusses value-added services for e-books and provides a case study for the creative cooperation model for industry.
- The goal of the experimental method was to find out popular interaction designs for mobile value-added services. It showed that participants' opinions of e-books were fairly neutral in user testing.
- The analysis of the search moves revealed that several participants experienced difficulty finding the topic pages devoted to different types of value-added services. It offers the features of value-added services for the development and improvement of interactive e-books in the future.

THE E-BOOK OF RICH INTERACTION DESIGN FOR IPAD

E-book technology offers a new way for book delivery to readers, whereby a digital copy of a book (e-book) is delivered to a device that a consumer uses (Jiang & Katsamakos, 2010). Publishers are using the Digital Publishing Suite from Adobe to create publications that integrate the design fidelity of print with the interactivity of digital, such as WIRED MAGAZINE ("WIRED MAGAZINE," 2010), Martha Stewart

Living("Martha Stewart Living Magazine," 2011), ELLE Taiwan("ELLE TAIWAN," 2011). This paper analysis many types of e-book readers have been developed for iPad device, such as WIRED MAGAZINE("WIRED MAGAZINE," 2010), Martha Stewart Living("Martha Stewart Living Magazine," 2011), ELLE Taiwan("ELLE TAIWAN," 2011), CAR NEWS("CAR NEWS," 2011) and FHM TAIWAN("FHM TAIWAN," 2011).

NOVEL HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERFACE DESIGN

Interactive e-books offer a variety of interactive types, which is the application of gestures to communicate with the touch screen on the iPad (Wroblewski, 2010). Below, we have listed important gestures (see Figure 1) for basic operation of the touch screen to help users understand a compelling and interesting interface design:

Figure 1. Gesture operation on touch screen.

Tap

To tap the touch screen, briefly touch the surface with a fingertip. This is often used in switch functions, buttons, pages, and content, etc.

Double tap

To double tap the touch screen, rapidly touch surface twice with a fingertip. This is seldom used when reading e-books on the iPad.

Flick

To flick the touch screen, quickly brush the surface with a fingertip. This is often used in content and page switching.

Drag

To drag the touch panel, move a fingertip over the surface without losing contact. This is often used for viewing pictures from different angles or reading content.

Pinch and spread

To pinch the touch screen, touch the surface with two fingers and bring them closer together. To spread the touch screen, touch the surface with two fingers and move them apart.

POPULAR USER INTERFACE ELEMENTS

Tapping the touch screen with a finger is the simplest gesture in the iPad. It is often used in functional switching, button behavior, page switching, and content switching. Currently popular types are tapping the touchscreen and then flying into the content from the outside, and tapping on a thumbnail to switch the content and see a bigger picture, watching step by step instructions and pictures, showing text information, viewing device profiles, playing animations, music or videos, tapping yes Or no answer questions, tapping A or B buttons for psychological testing, tapping button link online questionnaires, Q & A, guessing games, and showing maps. This study analyzes the popular user interface design as follows:

Tap and get different article or image

Interactive e-books have a simple and convenient operational design. Users can use tap pictures, numbers and symbols to read their favorite content on the iPad (see Figure 2). It uses button behavior to control the content for the screen size and layout on the iPad, and it allows users to switch between different articles or images using gestures.

Figure 2. Tap pictures, numbers and symbols to read their favorite content.

Tap to read animation element

Colorful interactive books have broken the traditional static graphic content by integrating a variety of material in the digital content. Users can

tap a finger to watch diverse and dynamic content, such as animations, music and video on the screen (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Tap a finger to watch diverse and dynamic content.

Tap and get information from your questionnaire

Interactive e-books provide more diverse value-added services that can be used to carry out surveys, Q&A, riddles, games and other psychological tests (see Figure 4). Users can engage in psychological testing to understand themselves, or through simple games get more interesting interactive content.

Figure 4. Read a question and tap an option until the end of psychological testing. You can see result on your next.

Tap and get special services

Users can tap the screen to access links to websites, facebook and blogs, and then enter their e-mail address to get the latest information and content (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Enter their e-mail address to get the latest information.

Double tap to open tool menus

Double tapping the touch screen is the least-used gesture on the iPad. It is currently only used to open tool menus (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Double tap to open tool menus.

Flick for jump to next page quickly

Flick is often used for page switching. It can let the user jump to next page quickly.

Drag to view exclusive object and panorama

Dragging the touch screen with a finger is often used for viewing objects, pictures and panorama from different angles (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Drag to view objects, pictures and panorama from different angles.

Pinch and spread to view detail and scale image

Pinching and spreading the touch screen can adjust the scale of images and view complete objects or special interactive content.

The above findings are summarized in the following:

- Switch content: Users often want to change between articles and images or display animation effects using tap or flick gestures.
- Display hidden content: Tapping is usually used to display or hide content, and dragging left and right or up and down is used to show hidden articles and images.
- Show detailed content: Users often use pinch and spread gestures to present detailed content.
- Link: Tapping is the most popular gesture for links to new pages, websites, facebook, and blogs, etc.

METHODS

User testing involves measuring the performance of typical users doing typical tasks in controlled laboratory-like conditions. Its goal is to obtain objective performance data to show how usable a system or product is in terms of usability goals, such as ease of use or learnability (Preece, Rogers, & Sharp, 2002). User testing is an applied form of experimentation used by developers to test whether the product they develop is usable by the intended user population to achieve their tasks (Dumas & Redish, 1999). Therefore, this study intended to research touch screen user experiences with subjects who have conducted user testing.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SELECTION METHOD

Typically 5-12 users are involved in user testing (Dumas & Redish, 1999), but often there are fewer and compromises are made to work within budget and schedule constraints. In user testing the time it takes typical users to complete clearly defined, typical tasks is measured and the number and type of errors they make are recorded. Often the routes that users take through tasks are also noted, particularly in web-searching tasks. Making sense of this data is helped by observational data, answers to user-satisfaction questionnaires and interviews, and key stroke logs, which is why these techniques are used along with user testing in

usability studies (Preece, et al., 2002). Therefore, this study selected seven users who had experience using touch screens to evaluate the interactive interface design for CAR NEWS on the iPad.

THE DESIGN TASKS

This paper presents an experiment designed to capture and compare instances of interaction design. Before starting the main tasks the participants were invited to explore e-books for up to five minutes and to think aloud as they moved through the site. Five tasks were used and the participants were given 30 minutes to use mobile value-added services. All participants used the same tool for the experiment. The participants were then asked to sit down, and the goals of the study and test procedure were explained. The researchers captured all of the operation screens using the Display Recorder for iPad app, which is the equivalent to screencasting software such as ScreenFlow but is designed for the iPad.

EXPERIMENT SET UP

Based on the literature on interactive e-books, the researchers attempted to find an interaction design of e-books with mobile value-added services. First, the researcher listed the main task and page of the interface design on CAR NEWS for iPad. The structured tasks were as follows:

- Task1: Find information about start apps by users in exploring CAR NEWS.
- Task2: Find information about tool menus by users in exploring CAR NEWS.
- Task3: Find information about reading content by users in exploring CAR NEWS.
- Task4: Find information about application of value-added services by users in exploring CAR NEWS.
- Task5: Find information about interaction design by users in exploring CAR NEWS.

In order to ensure proper testing behavior, the CAR NEWS page layout structure (see Figure 8 & Figure 9), the usage, and training of the experiment to be conducted were explained to the experiment participants before the formal experiment began.

Figure 8. The CAR NEWS of page layout structure for iPad.

In this experiment, we recorded the start time and completion time, error counts, gestures and any negative comments or mannerisms observed during the search when the participants read the e-book. Second, when all the tasks were completed, the participants were given an open-ended questionnaire about operation gestures, the content and the interaction design, and were then invited to make suggestions. In almost all designs, no matter for what, digital or

analog, interaction designers should strive to reflect the following set of adjectives. Certainly in some circumstances, some of these characteristics may not be appropriate you may not want a mission control panel to be playful, for example but in general, if a product or service can be described with these adjectives, it is likely an example of good interaction design(Saffer, 2006). We analyzed and selected the suitable characteristics of good interaction design for the e-books about CAR NEWS on the iPad. These would typically include:

- Trustworthy : Humans likely make decisions about the trustworthiness of a product or service within seconds of engaging with it. Indeed, recent research has suggested that humans make snap judgments in less than a second. Products and services have to display their trustworthiness quickly.
- Appropriate: The solutions that interaction designers come up with need to be appropriate to the culture, situation, and context that they live in. All of these factors can drastically affect the type of product or service.
- Smart: The products and services we use need to be smarter than we are. They have to prevent us from making mistakes or from working harder than we need to. They need to do the work we

Figure 9. The task testing of user's search path.

can't easily do alone. They have to be smart.

- **Clever:** Clever products and services predict the needs of their users and then fulfill those needs in unexpectedly pleasing ways. Its designers anticipated how users would enjoy the service and designed it with cleverness in mind. An excellent example of this sort of design is its eight-second rewind button. The first time viewers use the clever eight-second rewind button, they typically are hooked on the feature.
- **Pleasurable:** Unless a product or service is pleasing to use, we likely won't use it often unless we have to (say, for our work or well being). In design terms, products and services can be pleasing in two ways: aesthetically and functionally.

Finally, according to Saffer in 2006, we proposed the characteristics of good interaction design to find out the characteristics of CAR NEWS for iPad. This paper offers features and services for the development and improvement of interactive design on mobile devices. Recording and analyzing the data focused on such areas as:

- Analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of CAR NEWS for iPad.
- Collecting novel human-computer interface designs and popular gestures used to read e-books.
- Using the five characteristics of good interaction design, proposed by Saffer in 2006, as an index to evaluate the CAR NEWS interface.
- Archiving the interactive design characteristics of interactive e-books for mobile devices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Task analysis is especially useful as a check to see whether the design supports all the tasks required. Rare but important tasks often get overlooked, but with a task analysis, the designer can make sure the design meets all the requirements(Saffer, 2006). We organized practical user evaluations within the setup using seven males as the subject users. All of these users had experience using the multi- touch screen of the iPad. This study investigated the background information and tested a series of tasks about interaction design using CAR NEWS for iPad.

RESULTS OF USER TESTING

As CAR NEWS provides information about domestic and foreign cars, and its main readers are male, seven male users with an average age of 30.9 years were invited to participate in the experiment. Users' performance on the structured tasks was analyzed in detail and participant ratings were tabulated. The participants rated the tasks on a scale of 1-4, where 1=easy, 2=ok, 3=difficult, and 4=needed help. The researchers recorded all of the operating gestures and problems with interface usability that came forth in the evaluation. Table 1 shows the experiment results of the structured tasks for CAR NEWS. The results showed an average score of 1.5, indicating that the participants felt the tasks were between easy and ok. However, there was one user who needed help in task 4 to change the screen orientation of the iPad from vertical to horizontal. There were two users who needed help in task 4 to tap the thumbnails and view each big image. There was one user who needed help in task 5 to move to the second page of the tenth stack and drag it left and right or up and down to show hidden articles and images.

Participant number	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	Average
Background Information								
Sex	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	7M
Age	33	30	28	31	30	31	33	30.9
Experience with e-books	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	4Y,3N
Experience with multi-touch screen	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	7Y
Experience with iPad	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	3Y,4N
Structured tasks								
Task 1:								
Start CAR NEWS apps	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.0
Check screen is vertical orientation	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.0
Task 2:								
To read the help	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1.1
Double tap to show tool menus	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1.1
Tap content button to show catalog	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.0
Task 3:								

Enter the first page of the sixth stack	1	3	2	2	2	2	1	1.9
Flick to the second page	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1.7
Tap plus symbol to read and then close the dialog box	2	1	1	1	2	1	3	1.6
Task 4:								
Enter the first page of the eighth stack	1	3	1	2	2	2	1	1.7
Change your screen orientation of the iPad from vertical to horizontal	1	1	4	2	1	2	2	1.9
Tap the thumbnails and view each big image	1	4	4	1	1	2	1	2.0
Task 5:								
Enter the first page of the tenth stack	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1.1
Find out video	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.0
Play video	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.1
Move to the second page of the tenth stack	1	4	1	2	2	2	2	2.0
Drag it left and right or up and down to show hidden articles and images	1	4	1	2	2	2	2	2.0
Participant Average	1.2	1.9	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.5

Table 1. Experiment results of structured tasks for CAR NEWS

In this study, the participants operated each task and the number of errors encountered was recorded in detail. Table 2 shows the error count for the users exploring CAR NEWS for iPad. The results showed that the most common errors (Error d) occurred in task 4, because the users did not know how to switch between article and images and were not accustomed to this method of reading. The following reasons were given:

- Error a: Users could not understand the plus sign was a button, as there were no obvious prompts on the page (see Figure 10).
- Error b: Users would not be able to view e-books when they did not stop video playback.
- Error c: Users could not understand the sorting method and easily lost track of where e-books were located.

- Error d: Users did not know how to switch between articles and images.
- Error e: No page numbers and the direction of the guidelines created reading difficulties.
- Error f: if the user moved the screen to the horizontal position, it would be easy to make an error.
- Error g: Users could not move pages left or right, and they had to return to the top of the page.
- Error h: The scroll icon was unclear, and users did not know they could move images left and right (see Figure 11).
- Error i: Users did not know where the help files were located.

Figure 10. The plus sign of CAR NEWS's content.

Figure 11. The scroll icon was unclear of CAR NEWS's content.

Participant number	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	Average
Task1	-	-		1 (e)	-	-	-	0.14
Task2	-	1 (i)	1 (e)	-	-	-	-	0.29
Task3	-	1 (c)	1 (c)	-	-	-	2 (a,e)	0.57
Task4	1 (a)	2 (c,d)	1 (f)	1 (f)	1 (d)	1 (g)	-	1
Task5	1 (b)	1 (b)	1 (e)	-	-	-	1 (h)	0.57

Table 2. The error count by users of structured tasks for CAR NEWS

Table 3 shows the time spent, problems and suggestions by users in exploring CAR NEWS on the iPad. There were three users (participant A, participant C, and participant G) who quickly completed the tasks because they had experience using the iPad. Participant G needed only 4:44 to complete the tasks, because he read e-books nearly every day on an iPad. There were four users who needed more time to complete the tasks, and two users needed help because they rarely read e-books on an iPad. Participant E took 23:15 to complete the tasks, because he was not used to reading e-books and he preferred reading traditional books.

Participant number	Problems and suggestions	Time
A	Users could not notice the plus sign is a button, as it is not an obvious prompt on the page. Therefore, designers should provide a more visible image button or prompt.	07:56
B	Users cannot understand the sorting method and easily lose e-books. Therefore, designers should add an introduction and description page.	19:27
C	No page numbers and the direction of the guidelines create reading difficulties. Therefore, designers should add chapter numbers.	06:57
D	Most of the pages can only be read in the vertical position. Therefore, e-books should play and read in both the vertical and horizontal positions.	19:49
E	Users are not free to change the text size. Therefore, designers should provide the possibility of changing fonts.	23:15
F	Users are not free to control the image size. Therefore, all images should contain a zoom function.	18:56
G	Catalog page content can be read directly, but users cannot return to the previous page. Therefore, designers should add an undo key for quick undo. Users who want to read the stack content must return to the top page and then jump to another stack. Therefore, designers should offer a user-friendly interface.	04:44

Table 3. The results of time spent, problems and suggestions by users in exploring CAR NEWS on the iPad.

Table 4 shows the results of gesture type (Tap=T, Double tap=D1, Flick=F, Drag=D2, Pinch=P and Spread=S) during the tasks in exploring CAR NEWS on the iPad. The results showed that most users performed the tap gesture when reading e-books. Users often selected articles, images and buttons by intuitively tapping the screen, because they had experience with the concept of a click button. Most users also used the flick gesture in switching between e-book pages. They already had experience with touch screens, and were accustomed to using a finger to flick the screen quickly. Users could use a double tap gesture to jump to content, use a tap gesture to select the content button for the next stack, and then use a flick gesture to move to a specific page in each task. As most tasks and procedures also provided instructions for the gestures, the users could intuitively use gestures to complete the tasks. However, at the beginning of the experiment, the researchers did not clearly indicate

the gestures and instructions for some structured tasks, and this could account for the participants being unable to react properly the first time. For example, participant A and participant B were confused about the location of the help button, which caused repeated operations and gestures, and a large number of unnecessary steps during task 2. In addition, participant G often used pinch and spread gestures on the images, and he wanted to zoom in and out of images, but CAR NEWS did not support this function, such as in task 4: tapping the thumbnails to view each large image.

Participant number	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Task 1:							
Start CAR NEWS apps	T	T	T	T	T	T	T
check screen is vertical orientation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Task 2:							
To read the help	T, D1, F	F, D1	F	F	F	F	F
Double tap to show tool menus	D1						
Tap content button to show catalog	T	T	T	T	T	T	T
Task 3:							
Enter the first page of the sixth stack	T, D1, F						
Flick to the second page	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
Tap plus symbol to read and then close the dialog box	T	T, D1	T, D1	T	T	T	T
Task 4:							
Enter the first page of the eighth stack	T, D1, F						
Change your screen orientation of the iPad from vertical to horizontal	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Tap the thumbnails and view each big image	T	T	T	T	T	T	T, P, S
Task 5:							
Enter the first page of the tenth stack	T, D1, F						
Find out video	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Play video	T	T	T	T	T	T	T
Move to the second page of the tenth stack	F	F, D2	F	F	F	F	F
Drag it left and right or up and down to show hidden articles and images	D2						

Table 4. The results of gesture type about tasks testing by users in exploring CAR NEWS on the iPad.

Interactive e-books have ever-changing content, and they focus on the interaction design and value-added services for the user. This study investigated interaction design and the interface operating features of interactive e-books. The survey showed the most popular interactive gesture on the iPad was the tap gesture. It is convenient and quick to use, and it offers intuitive interface operations without learning, and it has been widely used in e-book operation design.

This study concluded the features of value-added services for creating interactive e-books on the iPad as follows:

- Operation gestures: As tapping is simple and quick, it is widely used in operational designs. The most popular applied design is content switching and displaying hidden content.
- Content planning: Using the concept of theme-style stacks for presentation, and providing interesting and diverse digital content, including video, animation, music, and images.
- Interaction design: This should be based on interesting interactions, such as questionnaires, puzzles, psychometrics, games and other interactive games.

RESULTS OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR GOOD INTERACTION DESIGN

This study investigated user opinions on the characteristics (Trustworthy, Appropriate, Smart, Clever and Pleasurable) of good interaction designs for CAR NEWS. Table 5 shows the results (Very disagreed, Disagreed, Neutral, Agreed and Very agreed) of the characteristics for good interaction design. Most users agreed that the results of user testing had the characteristics of good interaction design. The results showed that there were five users who felt CAR NEWS had the appropriate characteristics. They are explained as follows:

- Participant A: User reading content is attractive because it has appropriate context and copious content, such as articles, images, video, sound and animation.
- Participant B: CAR NEWS has appropriate situations because it offers a lot of videos and in-depth explanations of content for users to enjoy.

- Participant D: CAR NEWS has appropriate content, and most of the reading moves in the same direction, so users do not have to change direction.
- Participant E: CAR NEWS has appropriate interaction designs, but the tool menus should show the whole text, which can serve readers in Taiwan.
- Participant G: CAR NEWS has appropriate articles, but he prefers switching pages from left to right, like when reading a traditional book.

The results showed that there were four users who remained neutral about the characteristics. They agreed that CAR NEWS had a smart design, but it did not display pages well, and users easily got lost.

Characteristics	Very disagreed	Disagreed	Neutral	Agreed	Very agreed
Trustworthy		1	2	3	1
Appropriate			2	5	
Smart	1		4	2	
Clever		1	3	1	2
Pleasurable		1	2	2	1

Table 5. Experiment results of characteristics for good interaction design.

The results showed that the users agreed on the trustworthy, appropriate, smart, clever and pleasurable characteristics of CAR NEWS. CAR NEWS classified content and advertising separately, but the classification was not clear, leading to difficulty in reading and in the usage of the interface. Therefore, e-books should contain clear illustrations to guide readers. They should provide some interactive information to give readers a sense of participation and rich content for reading. The study concluded that the characteristics of good interaction design for mobile devices are as follows:

Trustworthy

Users can choose the content through the catalog’s link. CAR NEWS provides an interactive display of its contents, and allows users to read the full text of the products and value-added services. Most of the interactive operations of CAR NEWS can be intuitive, so it is trustworthy with regards to recognition features.

Appropriate

CAR NEWS has appropriate cultural, situational and article contexts in the interactive design, in which user reading content can easily be attracted.

Smart

CAR NEWS is very smart for interactive design, and users can quickly use it with gestures; however, it is easy to get lost when reading.

Clever

CAR NEWS does not have a limited page size for interaction design, and users can browse with the use of gestures to get more content.

Pleasurable

CAR NEWS breaks traditional methods to let users feel happy and provide more detailed information for users.

CONCLUSIONS

This study concluded the features (operation gestures, content plan and interaction design) of value-add services for creating interactive e-books on the iPad as follows:

- Operation gestures: Tapping is widely used in operation design because it is simple and quick.
- Content plan: A good layout design is necessary to provide complete, interesting and diverse content, including video, animation, music, and images.
- Interaction design: It is very important to offer interesting interactions, such as questionnaires, puzzles, psychometrics, games and other interactive games.

This study provided the characteristics of good interaction design in reading e-books for iPad. The subjects of the study were seven users who independently evaluated CAR NEWS on the iPad. We compiled their comments and discussed with them about their findings in a meeting, obtaining suggestions from them on strategies for addressing problems. The following are some important points of their findings:

- Trustworthy: There are trustworthy and simple operation modes for interaction designs that provide rich content to users.

- Appropriate: There are quick and easy operation modes for interaction designs that provide appropriate arrangements to users.
- Smart: Users often cannot find the page to read and easily get lost.
- Clever: It can quickly predict user demands.
- Pleasurable: Breaking the traditional model provides a good interactive design.

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